

The minimally meaningful effect size: A vital component of pre-registrations

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An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Given widespread concerns regarding the reproducibility of scientific results, pre-registration has emerged as a valuable tool to enhance open-science research and improve scientific rigour. However, one element that remains largely absent from pre-registrations is the explicit incorporation of effect size magnitude, particularly the minimally meaningful effect size (MMES). Including an MMES within pre-registrations encourages researchers to make a priori considerations about the smallest effect size that would be considered practically significant within the context of their study. This minimum threshold depends on specific contextual factors, such as research design, measurement tools, and intended application of the findings, all of which influence how effect size magnitude should be interpreted. By specifying the MMES in advance, researchers are less likely to engage in haphazard interpretation of effect sizes after results are known. This practice, referred to as HIMEing, involves modifying post hoc what is considered meaningful and is regarded as a questionable research practice. The incorporation of MMES values in pre-registration protocols not only enhances transparency and interpretive clarity but also promotes more thoughtful evaluation of practical significance. In this paper, we outline the rationale for integrating MMES into pre-registrations and argue that its inclusion strengthens methodological integrity. To illustrate this process, we present a worked example using a previously published study, demonstrating how researchers can meaningfully define and justify an MMES as part of their pre-registered research plan.

Keywords: effect size; methodology; open science; pre-registration; reproducibility

Pre-registration of research/statistical methods has been seen as a way to improve research practices by limiting the possibility of questionable research practices (QRPs) while also enhancing a study's ability to be replicated (Miguel et al., 2014; Munafò et al., 2017; Nosek et al., 2012; Yamada, 2018). Although pre-registration can be a resource for limiting QRPs in research, the way researchers are currently using pre-registrations does not ensure that they address issues related to interpreting the magnitude of effect size.

In this paper, we argue that incorporating the minimally meaningful effect size (MMES; also known as the smallest effect of interest, or SESOI, and, in health-related clinical trials, the minimal clinically important difference, MCID) into pre-registrations can aid researchers in understanding how to interpret the magnitude of an effect size. More specifically, researchers stating a priori the minimum criteria that must be met for a study's effect size to be meaningful is a valuable strategy for encouraging researchers to consider what effect magnitude is important before conducting a study. The current study uses the term MMES, rather than alternatives, since this term appears to be the first used in the literature to represent the minimally meaningful effect size; it appeared in the literature around the early 2000s (e.g., Baxter et al., 2003; Pendergrass et al., 2003).

This paper will first provide a very brief introduction to QRPs. Next, we discuss the value of pre-registration for dealing with QRPs and other issues. Following that, we introduce a new QRP relevant to interpreting the magnitude of observed effects. Fourth, we discuss how and where the MMES should be incorporated into a pre-registration. Lastly, we provide an example of how to integrate the MMES into a pre-registration.

Questionable research practices and the replication crisis

A QRP introduces various design, analytic, or reporting practices that can have harmful implications for evidence-based science, the development of theory, and the overall perceptions of the rigour of scientific research (Banks et al., 2016; Chin et al., 2021). Some examples of commonly employed QRPs include Hypothesizing After the Results are Known (HARKing), *p*-hacking, and cherry-picking (Gadbury & Allison, 2012; Kerr, 1998). It can be argued that the prevalence of QRPs in research was partially responsible for a formidable methodological controversy known as the replication crisis (also referred to as the reproducibility crisis or the crisis of confidence; Fanelli, 2018) where researchers were unable to obtain findings similar to earlier studies during tailored replication studies (Hensel, 2021).

Preregistering research protocols

The pre-registration of research protocols (or just pre-registration) has been a valuable tool that can remedy some of the problems associated with QRPs and the replication crisis. More specifically, having researchers state their aims, sampling plans, hypotheses, and analysis plans a priori can be a powerful approach to combat prevalent QRPs (Miguel et al., 2014). Since the important elements of the study are identified before the experiment is conducted, practices like HARKing, *p*-hacking and cherry-picking are easily visible to readers, reviewers, editors, etc. (Bakker et al., 2020; Yamada, 2018). The Open Science Framework (OSF) has led the future of open-source research by providing a platform for researchers to open-source their work. For example, the OSF provides pre-registration templates that are very popular among researchers. Over the past decade, pre-registrations have doubled annually, with around 40 pre-registrations completed in 2012 to more than 40000 completed at the end of 2019 (Bakker et al., 2020). Bakker et al. (2020) further goes on to state how the most effective pre-registrations are often challenging and time-consuming compared to more simplistic registrations. The pre-registration process is still relatively novel, and new methodologies are consistently being employed to maximise the potential of a pre-registration. Through the use of pre-registration documents, researchers are taking the necessary steps toward a more ethical and legitimised research process.

Haphazard Interpretation of the Magnitude of Effect Size (HIME)

As previously mentioned, pre-registration is an option to minimise the effect of various QRPs in a research study. However, one area of the research process that has yet to receive much attention is the interpretation of the magnitude of effect sizes (Beribisky et al., 2019; Pek & Flora, 2018). An effect size can be defined as “a quantitative reflection of a magnitude of some phenomenon that is used to address a question of interest” (Kelley & Preacher, 2012, p. 140). Researchers typically make no interpretations regarding magnitude, or rely on procedures with questionable validity (Farmus et al., 2022). These questionable approaches may include using benchmark standards for interpreting effect size magnitude (e.g., small, medium, and large interpretations, see Lachenbruch & Cohen, 1989) or interpreting magnitude by comparing the effect size in a given study to the distribution of effect sizes in a discipline or research area (Panzarella et al., 2021).

More precisely, haphazardly interpreting the magnitude of effect sizes (HIMEing) can impact the interpretation of a particular finding by distorting the true practical significance of the effect (i.e., meaningfulness within the context of research). This paper proposes HIMEing as a new QRP that can drastically affect how researchers perceive and interpret the importance of reported effects. For example, an author may HIME by interpreting magnitude based on statistical significance, published cut-offs for effect sizes, or comparing the magnitude of effect sizes to the distribution of effect sizes in a given field. Each of these concepts will be elaborated on below. As pre-registrations have been a reliable tool to handle various QRPs, incorporating the MMES into pre-registrations may help prevent HIMEing in research. More specifically, incorporating an MMES into a pre-registration imposes a quantitative value that serves as the minimum criteria that must be met for a study's effect size magnitude to be deemed meaningful within the context of the study. We now expand on some common ways that researchers may succumb to HIMEing.

Statistical Significance does not equal practical significance. Inferring the practical significance or meaningfulness of an effect solely based on statistical significance is an example of HIMEing. Statistical significance often provides little to no evidence regarding an effect's meaningfulness or practical significance (Spence & Stanley, 2018). More specifically, statistical significance examines if the findings from a study are likely due to chance, while effect size explains the magnitude of the effects (Sullivan & Feinn, 2012). The American Statistical Association noted, “while the p-value can be a useful statistical measure, it is commonly misused and misinterpreted” (Wasserstein & Lazar, 2016, p. 131). Null hypothesis statistical test results should not factor into interpretations regarding effect size magnitude.

Using Published Conventions to Assess Magnitude. Additionally, researchers commonly engage in HIMEing by adopting published benchmarks, e.g., small, medium, and large, for assessing magnitude. Lachenbruch and Cohen's (1989) “convention approach” advocates employing benchmark effect sizes when a study is novel, and there are limited studies in that particular area (Lachenbruch & Cohen, 1989). Employing benchmark values for interpreting effect size magnitude can become troublesome as it is common practice for researchers to misuse these benchmark terms. Cohen (1988) suggested only employing these “arbitrary conventions for use only when no better basis for estimating effect size is available” (p. 12). Although this approach is highly utilized due to its simplistic nature, the researcher again circumvents correctly interpreting the magnitude of the effects of a given study (Pek & Flora, 2018). Furthermore, researchers' reliance on established benchmark values in psychological research often lacks practical relevance to the context of their specific research questions. Consequently, without contextually grounded interpretations, researchers' ability to comprehend the magnitude of their effect sizes' practical significance and implications is significantly limited.

Assessing Magnitude via Comparisons with Past Research. Another common way researchers fall under the fallacies of HIMEing is by interpreting magnitude via the “comparison approach”. This approach has been popularised by articles that summarise the distribution, including the central tendency, of effect sizes within specific fields/disciplines (e.g., Hemphill, 2003; Pogrow, 2019). For example, Hemphill extended Lachenbruch and Cohen's benchmarks by deriving the empirical distribution of correlation coefficients from psychological studies. Hemphill used this distribution to obtain benchmark values for correlations within the field. This approach encourages researchers to interpret effect size relative to the distribution of effect sizes within a given field (see Panzarella et al., 2021, for examples). For example, let's say a researcher conducts a social psychology experiment

and compares their effect sizes to the average effect size across all social psychology studies. In our opinion, this comparison provides no useful information regarding the practical significance (magnitude) of the effect under study, as the nature/contexts of the studies likely vary widely.

Comparing effect sizes and effect size magnitude across studies is important and valuable, however, effect sizes from past studies should not be used to determine the magnitude of current effect sizes. Magnitude should only be based on the context of the current research. Whether the effect is small or large relative to other effects found within a given area of research does not say anything about the meaningfulness of an effect within the context of a specific study. Hence, the interpretation of effect size within the context of previous research fails to provide valid interpretations of magnitude (Simpson, 2018) and is an example of HIMEing.

Ignoring Effect Size Precision. Another example of HIMEing is not considering the precision associated with a given effect size. For example, an effect size with a very wide confidence interval provides little information regarding the nature of the effect. Let's say a researcher is measuring the effect of depression (mean item score on a 7-point Likert scale) on academic performance (GPA on a 0-100 scale) and finds that for every one-point increase in depression, academic performance is reduced by 5 points. This might be a very practically important and meaningful effect, but before statements are made regarding the practical significance of the relationship, the precision around the effect should be considered (Amrhein et al., 2019). For instance, a confidence interval that ranges from 4.9 to 5.1 would be interpreted substantially differently from one that ranges from 1 to 9. Thus, presenting effect size measures without estimates of precision can mislead readers and is a clear example of HIMEing.

How to utilise the “in-context interpretation” approach

As interpreting the practical significance of a study can be problematic with the set of practices outlined above, it is best to analyse the magnitude of an effect by scrutinising the real-world meaning (Baguley, 2009; Lachenbruch & Cohen, 1989; Schäfer & Schwarz, 2019). This approach is coined “in-context interpretation.” Researchers are encouraged to form a subjective interpretation of the meaningfulness of the effects of a study by considering all aspects regarding the context of the study, including aspects internal (e.g., design, measurement) and external (e.g., practical significance) to the study.

Aspects internal to the study can include the research question, design (e.g., randomised controlled trial vs observational study), sample size (i.e., precision), measurement (e.g., reliability and validity of measurement tools), etc. Aspects external to the study include everything related to practical significance (real-world importance); a study researching strategies to improve memory might highlight the implications of the memory improvements on quality of life, work-related activities, social relationships, etc, whereas a study comparing treatments for depression might highlight the practical advantages of the recommended treatment (e.g., relative nature/magnitude of symptom improvement, perceived symptom improvement from the perspective of family/friends).

Durlak (2009) offers three guidelines that can aid researchers in evaluating effect sizes through an in-context approach. The first step is to take into account the source, specifically the calibre of the research that is generating the effect size. This encompasses both recent discoveries and previous pertinent research. Second, researchers need to understand how authors of related studies connected the context of their study to its effect size magnitude; in other words, what contextual factors have previously been found to be relevant in understanding the magnitude of an effect. The final guideline is to consider the practical implications and significance of the study; a study whose findings have the potential to lead to radical (and potentially expensive) policy changes might be interpreted differently from an exploratory study of a potentially new association among variables.

As well, there have been numerous methods for interpreting effect size magnitude across different fields of research using the in-context approach. A cost-benefit analysis is one approach that is valuable for both applied and basic research (Anvari & Lakens, 2021). For applied research, the cost-benefit analysis can be used to determine the size of an effect that is considered beneficial enough compared to the costs (e.g., money, time commitment or training and development). This approach can be extended to basic research by establishing a clear goal and considering what effect size value would be necessary to have the goal met. However, it is important to separate the generic interpretation of the meaningfulness of an effect from the cost-benefit interpretation of the meaningfulness of an effect, as these have different meanings but can vary substantially. An

additional method employs a subjective anchor-based approach to estimate minimal differences to provide subjective global rankings of change (Anvari & Lakens, 2021). This method relates a client's amount of change (e.g., change from pretest to post-test on a relevant clinical measure) to an anchor (e.g., whether a therapist deems that the individual has improved, stayed the same, or even deteriorated). This is not a comprehensive list of all ways to evaluate effect size measurements using the in-context approach, but these examples capture some typical approaches that can be adopted in psychological research.

Consider a fictional example of interpreting an effect size value for research on enhancing reading literacy in children. The difficulty of a book is represented by an arbitrary level that ranges from 1 (very easy) to 10 (very challenging) to aid children in gauging the strength of their reading skills. Assume that the researcher is judging the effectiveness of 20 minutes of daily reading, for one month, on children's level of reading literacy and finds that this reading resulted in an average increase of two levels in reading comprehension. If researchers utilise the in-context interpretation approach, some of the following questions may be of interest: Was the sample representative of the population? Was 20 minutes per day an appropriate amount of time to observe the effect? Did participants closely follow the regimen? Did the selection of the specific books used to affect the magnitude of the results? Are two levels of increase in reading literacy important? What are the specific consequences of a two-level increase? How many levels do children reach in that time span without any intervention? How does reading literacy increase using this method compared to others? Is a 2-level increase enough relative to the cost of initializing this reading initiative? How much variability in the treatment effect was observed across the sample? This small subset of potentially important questions highlights the rigorous process that researchers can adopt to move from having results to being able to form a representative interpretation of magnitude (Panzarella et al., 2021).

Incorporating an MMES into pre-registrations

As discussed above, HIMEing is a QRP that can have substantial negative consequences in terms of understanding an effect's practical significance or meaningfulness. For example, exaggerating the importance of an effect could lead to policy changes or program initiations, which could be costly with little benefit, or minimizing the importance of an effect could lead to missed opportunities. More specifically, researchers will have a priori determined what magnitude of effect is expected to be meaningful, which can aid in interpreting the practical importance of effect sizes below or above the MMES. It is important to reiterate that studies with similar research hypotheses and theoretical backgrounds may nevertheless have very different contexts. These distinct contextual factors will almost always impact how the MMES is interpreted (Durlak, 2009).

Pre-registrations have previously been used as a tool to minimise QRPs (e.g., *p*-hacking), and incorporating the MMES can similarly help prevent HIMEing in research. When deciding which effects require a pre-registered MMES, researchers should ensure that effects relating to the primary research questions all include an MMES. Further, any secondary/exploratory effects for which magnitude is of interest (e.g., the findings have implications for policy/decisions) should also include an a priori MMES to reduce the likelihood of HIMEing. As all relevant hypotheses are encouraged to include an a priori MMES, researchers should be committed to publishing results regardless of whether their MMES aligns with initial hypotheses or demonstrates non-meaningful effects. This principle aligns closely with registered reports, which prioritise study design and methodological rigour over the nature of the results. By employing registered reports and/or pre-registering hypotheses, MMES thresholds, and analysis plans before data collection, researchers can increase transparency, decrease the influence of publication bias, and reduce the likelihood of HIMEing. Furthermore, publishing studies with MMESs that diverge from the pre-registration or registered report can contribute to the broader scientific discourse by highlighting the nuances and complexities of research findings, ultimately enriching the field and informing future studies.

When considering incorporating an MMES into a pre-registration, it is important to highlight that this process is different from researchers conducting an a priori power analysis as part of a pre-registration. In the current OSF pre-registration template, there is an option to provide information regarding power analyses (which might be based on an MMES). However, the main objective of a power analysis is to find an appropriate sample size for the study of interest, not interpret effect size magnitude. Further, in a study conducted by Beribisky et al. (2019), less than 2% of articles listed an MMES as part of their power analyses (even though this practice is recommended; Dienes, 2014). For

this reason, separating the power analysis and MMES components of a pre-registration is vital to fully encompass the importance of these two facets for a research study.

Effect sizes can be unstandardised (e.g., raw difference in means, unstandardised regression coefficient) or standardised (e.g., standardised mean difference, standardised regression coefficient) (Pek & Flora, 2018; Schäfer & Schwarz, 2019). It is important to conceptualise the MMES as an unstandardised metric, wherever possible. In other words, when the units of the measurement tools from a study are meaningful, much more thorough interpretations can be provided than when converting effects to a standardized metric. For example, if we are talking about the difference in wages between men and women doing the same job, working in dollars and cents is straightforward since the audience understands the buying power of money within the specific context of the research (e.g., what year, what location, what currency, what job). Or, when evaluating the effect of reducing social media use on depression, quantifying how many fewer depressive experiences per week are reported after reducing teens' social media use by one hour per day is directly intuitive. On the other hand, it is not so obvious what difference in standard deviations would be a meaningful difference between males and females on wages or a meaningful reduction in depressive experiences.

Conceptualising the MMES as a standardised effect size may also increase the temptation of researchers to use published cutoffs for interpreting effect size magnitude (e.g., Lachenbruch & Cohen, 1989). In some contexts, such as quantifying the MMES where the effect size of interest is a correlation between two variables or the scale being used is arbitrary, standardisation is unavoidable (and therefore, the MMES will necessarily be in a standardised metric). However, in other instances, decisions made by researchers might affect the interpretability of the unstandardised effect. For example, using the average Likert response across several items on a scale/sub-scale (instead of using a total score) might save the ability to derive an MMES in unstandardised units. Overall, we simply contend that an unstandardised effect size metric be used whenever possible.

When including the MMES in the pre-registration, researchers need to provide detailed justifications for the chosen effect size. Simply stating the MMES as a quantitative value (e.g., the MMES is $r = 0.25$) without any further detail would do little to advance knowledge regarding meaningfulness within the specific context of the research. Instead, we propose that this measure of magnitude be communicated by following a three-question guideline. The questions that we suggest below can be used as a broad framework for researchers when employing an MMES in pre-registrations:

1. Have previous MMESs been defined for the same primary research question(s) that is(are) being addressed in the current research? If so, explain to what extent these effect size magnitudes are relevant within the specific context of this research.
2. Discuss which aspects of the context of the current study are relevant to selecting an appropriate MMES for each of the primary research question(s) being addressed; be specific in terms of how each aspect of the context could influence the concluded magnitude of each effect.
3. State the MMES for each primary research question in the study, including the relevant justification.

Pre-registration example

To illustrate what this procedure may look like, we use Experiment 1 from Riesthuis and Woods' (2024) article evaluating the illusory truth effect (people's tendency to interpret information as being more truthful if it has been repeated, relative to information only presented once). In Part 1 of the experiment, participants were asked to classify 63 statements as either facts or opinions; these statements were a mix of misinformation, general opinion, and information statements. After a five-minute filler task, Part 2 of the experiment involved participants rating another 63 statements on truthfulness as measured on a 7-point Likert scale. Twenty-seven of the statements in Part 2 were repeated from Part 1, while 36 statements were novel. The goal of the study was to examine how prior exposure to statements affects perceived truthfulness across various types of statements (misinformation, general opinion, and general information). One of the analyses for Experiment 1 was a one-tailed paired-sample *t*-test comparing the average subjective truth rating between repeated statements and new statements.

Riesthuis and Woods (2024) pre-registered their method and proposed analyses (see <https://osf.io/kxyfn>). However, their preregistration justification for their MMES was limited relative

to the detail provided in their article. As discussed above, the preregistration should contain all relevant information regarding the magnitude of the MMES as well as the justification for selecting such a magnitude. Thus, below we augment the information provided in their preregistration using the three-question framework proposed above.

Have previous MMESs been defined for the same primary research question(s) that is(are) being addressed in the current research? If so, explain to what extent these effect size magnitudes are relevant within the specific context of this research.

Riesthuis and Woods (2024) cite no direct research that has defined previous MMESs for the same primary research questions that were addressed in their experiment. While they do cite past research on the illusory truth effect and COVID-19-related information which also used similar Likert measures (i.e., a seven-point scale, see Unkelbach & Speckmann, 2021), an MMES in that study was not defined.

Discuss which aspects of the context of the current study are relevant to selecting an appropriate MMES for each of the primary research question(s) being addressed; be specific in terms of how each aspect of the context could influence the concluded magnitude of each effect.

Although Riesthuis and Woods (2024) provide limited detail regarding the context in which they select an appropriate MMES in their preregistration, their published manuscript provides a detailed rationale for their selection of the MMES to evaluate the illusory truth effect. The rationale describes how the magnitude of the selected MMES (or SESOI) can lead to a meaningful shift in truth perception, factoring in how a question is framed, and how it would apply to different kinds of statements both together and separately. While this rationale is necessarily subjective, in that other researchers studying the illusory truth effect may not agree with the contextual variables selected or how they may apply to the MMES, transparently outlining this choice helps clarify subsequent interpretations of the results and decreases the potential for HIMEing.

Previous research has indeed shown that additional repetitions can increase the illusory truth effect (Hassan & Barber, 2021). Additionally, because we used ambiguous statements, a 0.2 increase in subjective truth ratings on a 7-point Likert scale can be crucial in whether participants deem the repeated information as the truth. Specifically, a 0.2 increase in subjective truth rating can push participants to judge an otherwise deemed untruthful or ambiguous statement (Likert score ≈ 4) toward the truthful side, especially when repeated multiple times. The cost of framing information in terms of a fact or an opinion is rather low and, therefore, a 0.2 increase in subjective truth can already be of interest. Moreover, the costs of simple instructions such as evaluating whether information is a fact or an opinion are also low. These simple instructions are of interest if they can increase people's subjective truth rating for correct information or protect them from judging, for example, opinions as more truthful. Since the effects of framing and encoding information can apply to both true information, misinformation, and general opinion statements, we deemed a 0.2 raw mean difference as the SESOI for the illusory truth effect when analysing all statement types together (true information, misinformation, and general opinion) but also when analysing the type of statements separately. (Riesthuis & Woods, 2024)

State the MMES for each primary research question in the study, including the relevant justification. The MMES for Experiment 1 is a 0.20 raw mean difference on a seven-point Likert scale.

Challenges involved with including an MMES in pre-registration

Although there are obvious advantages associated with implementing an MMES in pre-registration (e.g., prevent HIMEing), we acknowledge that the process will also be quite challenging for many researchers. First, as many researchers are new to the process of pre-registration, the quality of the pre-registration may not be high. Thankfully, previous research has demonstrated that although high-quality pre-registrations are preferable to lower-quality pre-registrations, partially specified pre-registrations may still be as effective as highly quality pre-registrations when addressing research malpractices like QRPs (Bakker et al., 2020). Researchers getting started with preregistering their hypotheses are encouraged to follow the guidelines provided by Nosek et al. (2012), DeHaven (2017), etc., as well as the preregistration forms available from the Center for Open Science (<https://www.cos.io/initiatives/prereg>) and as predicted (<https://aspredicted.org/>). It is important that researchers follow endorsed guidelines to establish valid and consistent preregistrations

(including a statement regarding relevant MMES values). Second, as researchers rarely consider MMES values in their current research (Beribisky et al., 2019; Farmus et al., 2022), conceptualising an MMES could be challenging. As such, this paper sought to provide a set of guidelines to aid researchers in conceptualising an MMES while emphasising the importance of understanding how the context of a research study impacts the effect sizes practical significance. Third, developing a context-dependent MMES may add even more complexity as benchmark effect sizes are still the standardized metric to interpret effect sizes due to their simplistic nature. For this reason, taking an “in-context interpretation” approach may be challenging as it is a relatively novel approach for interpreting effect size magnitude. Challenges with this approach may arise as this approach is more involved than simply selecting an effect size measure from a table of cut-offs for “small”, “medium” or “large”. Researchers across various fields of psychology are encouraged to develop thoughtful interpretations of a study’s effects by critically evaluating the context in relation to their specific research questions. Factors that may influence the magnitude of the MMES were discussed earlier in the manuscript, and we encourage researchers to carefully consider these when deriving an appropriate MMES value. In sum, we look forward to witnessing the many different approaches to defining and justifying a selected MMES within study pre-registrations.

CONCLUSION

There is little debate that pre-registrations are a valuable tool that can be utilised to mitigate various QRPs. To build upon this practice, incorporating an MMES into pre-registrations will encourage deep discussion regarding effect size magnitude and its practical significance while reducing the chance that HIMEing can impact interpretations of effect size magnitude. Although incorporating the MMES into pre-registrations has numerous advantages, there may be a concern that this recommendation will increase both the file drawer problem and publication bias. The conditions for these issues may be present when there is an inconsistency between the magnitude of the obtained effect size and what is deemed minimally meaningful in the pre-registration. Specifically, if an observed effect size is smaller in magnitude than the pre-registered MMES, the result can lead to the manuscript being biased against the publication process. We do not wish to add another mechanism that will perpetuate this issue. Instead, integrating the MMES into preregistration protocols could play a significant role in reducing publication bias. For instance, studies with non-statistically significant results but effect sizes meeting or exceeding the MMES are valuable contributions that warrant further exploration, potentially increasing their chances of publication. Conversely, studies with statistically significant findings that fail to meet the MMES may be deprioritised by journals due to their limited practical relevance or robustness, thus encouraging researchers to prioritize the contextual significance of their findings over merely achieving statistical significance. Importantly, as emphasised, a non-meaningful effect size does not diminish the value of a study. Research that prioritizes the contextual significance of their findings and still yields non-meaningful effect sizes can be equally valuable in guiding future analyses, shaping hypotheses, and enriching the broader body of knowledge.

In summary, we recommend that researchers pre-register the key elements of their study to mitigate the occurrence of malpractices in research. Furthermore, integrating the MMES into the pre-registration process will allow researchers to better comprehend and interpret effect size magnitudes and reduce the potential for HIMEing.

Acknowledgement: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Not applicable

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